

CHEMICAL INVESTIGATION OF *MUNDULEA SUBEROSA* BENTH.
PART I. ISOLATION AND CHARACTERISATION OF THE
ACTIVE PRINCIPLE FROM THE ROOT BARK

BY NARENDRA LAL DUTTA

A new compound, $C_{21}H_{18}O_4$, m.p. 193° , has been isolated from the root bark of *Mundulea suberosa* Benth in 0.3% yield and has been named 'munetone'. The substance has been found to be highly toxic to fish. The chemical nature of munetone is discussed. Two more substances* of m.p. $216-17^\circ$ and $74-75^\circ$ respectively were also isolated in a very poor yield.

Mundulea suberosa Benth [*Mundulea sericea* (Willd), Chevalier] of N. O. Leguminosae is a stout, erect shrub, with thick corky bark. The plant is well known to the natives of the Western Peninsula of India, Ceylon, Madagascar and Tropical Africa as far South as Mozambique, as an extremely efficient fish poison. Locally it is known as Surti or Supti' (Watts, "Dictionary of Economic Products of India", Calcutta, 1891, Part V, p. 288).

Quite a number of earlier workers (Tattersfield and Gittingham, *Ann. Appl. Biol.*, 1932, 19, 253; Worsley, *ibid.*, 1936, 23, 311; 1937, 24, 651; Tattersfield and Potter, *ibid.*, 1940, 27, 262; Greenway, Bull. of Misc. Information, No. 4, 1936, Royal Botanic Gardens, Kew) have examined the plant collected from various places and investigated the toxic action of the root, stem, bark, leaves and seeds to fish and insects. In certain cases *Mundulea* was found to be more poisonous than *Tephrosia vogelii* or rotenone-bearing plants in general. Meyer (*Rec. trav. chim.*, 1947, 66, 177) isolated from the stem-bark rotenone and a white substance ($C_{23}H_{20}O_7$, m.p. $193-95^\circ$) having a toxicity towards fish approaching that of rotenone. From the root bark, the latter substance together with a yellow crystalline compound of the same formula (m.p. 216°) were obtained. Indian samples were examined by Rao (D. Sc. Thesis, Andhra University, 1945), who isolated isorhamnetin and another substance ($C_{16}H_{20}O_6N$, m.p. 199°) from the leaves; he, however, failed to isolate any crystalline substance from either the seeds or the roots (*J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1954, 13A, 31). Bhima Rao (*Chem. Abs.*, 1940, 34, 3859) claimed to have obtained a crystalline substance from the active extract of *Mundulea suberosa*, and the phenylhydrazone, oxime and methyl derivatives were prepared. Recently Narayana and Rangaswami (*J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1955, 14B, 105) have reported the isolation of a crystalline substance (m.p. $180-82^\circ$) having a probable formula $C_{25}H_{24}O_6$ from the seeds of *Mundulea suberosa* Benth in 0.15% yield; the substance had a toxicity to fish approaching that of rotenone. A second crystalline substance (m.p. $187-89^\circ$) was also obtained as a minor component.

The present paper presents an account of the investigation of the root-bark of *Mundulea suberosa*, obtained from Badami (Bombay State), through the courtesy of the Forest Utilization Officer, Poona. As a result of the present work, the following three crystalline products* have been isolated.

* A preliminary note on the isolation of the products appeared in the *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1955, 14B, 424.

1. Munetone, $C_{21}H_{14}O_4$; long prisms, m.p. 192-93° yield 0.3% on the weight of the dry root bark.
2. The substance $C_{20}H_{14}O_6$; m.p. 216-17°, yellow needles, yield 0.001%.
3. The substance $C_{18}H_{26}O$; m.p. 74-75°, colorless microneedles, yield 0.002%.

The best method for the isolation of these products was through chromatography of the ether extractive of the root bark over alumina in anhydrous benzene. The usual methods of isolation through fractionation by different solvents resulted in all cases in the formation of dark coloured resins from which no crystalline product could be obtained. While the previous investigators (*loc. cit.*) made use of dilute alkali for the isolation of crystalline constituents from various parts of *Mundulea suberosa*, the present method avoids all such treatments and involves mildest possible operations.

Munetone contains one methoxy group. It is optically inactive and does not exhibit any coloration with ferric chloride. It cannot be acetylated or methylated. It forms an oxime but does not yield 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone derivative. It is insoluble in alkali and is unaffected with concentrated hydrochloric acid. In concentrated sulphuric acid it dissolves with a red colour. It shows a positive test with tetranitromethane and does not respond to Durham's test for rotenoids. The Wilson boric acid test was also negative. No coloration was produced by reduction of munetone with magnesium and hydrochloric acid, or with sodium amalgam and alcohol, but a yellow coloration was produced on addition of a few drops of H_2SO_4 (conc.) to a glacial acetic acid solution of the substance. It could not be reduced with platinum oxide catalyst in ethyl acetate solution. It did not react with iodine and potassium (or sodium) acetate or with N-bromosuccinimide, but easily formed a dibromo derivative in CCl_4 solution.

The yellow coloration produced by munetone with sulphuric acid and glacial acetic acid indicates that it may be an anthoxanthin. Dilute alkaline hydrolysis of munetone produces formic acid, characterised through the formaldehyde-chromotropic acid test, and a ketone (m.p. 128°) in about 93% yield. The detection of formic acid in the alkaline hydrolysate provided the clue of the possibility of an isoflavone constitution for the compound. The ketone was characterised through an oxime and was named 'munetol'. It analysed for $C_{20}H_{20}O_4$ and developed a deep green coloration with ferric chloride-alcohol. Unlike munetone, the Wilson boric acid test is positive in the case of munetol. The Wilson boric acid test is indicative of the grouping (I). The negative

test with the parent compound shows the absence in munetone of a hydroxyl group at position-5, which is essential for this test in an isoflavone nucleus. Genistein, biochanin A, osajin etc. furnish positive test, whereas ψ -baptigenin, tetrahydro-osajetin dimethyl

ether etc. exhibit no colour in the Wilson boric acid test. The fact that munetol shows this test is due to the closely related enolic system (II) as in the case of tetrahydro-qsajetin dimethyl ether (Wolfson *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 63, 1248) which also behaves similarly. The free hydroxyl group in position (a) of formula (II) is formed in the alkaline treatment. Further, on acetylation with acetic anhydride and sodium acetate for 3 hours at 145-50°, munetol affords a product (C₂₂H₂₀O₄, m.p. 227°) which evidently is not a simple acetyl derivative of munetol but agrees with the corresponding cyclised 2-methylisoflavone structure. From this it can be deduced that munetol is a derivative of *o*-hydroxyphenylbenzyl ketone. The ultraviolet absorption spectra of munetone show the maxima at 263 mμ (log ε, 4.61) and 330 mμ (log ε, 4.03), which are characteristic of an isoflavone structure (*Quart. Rev., Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 8, 71).

From the above chemical and physical properties, the partial structure of munetone and munetol may be tentatively represented as :

Munetone does not appear to agree with any of the compounds, so far isolated from various parts of *Mundulea suberosa*. Preliminary experiments indicate munetone to be highly toxic to fish. Further work on the constitution of munetone is in progress.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Isolation of the Crystalline Compounds.—The dried and powdered root-bark (480 g.) was extracted with ether at room temperature till the extract was colorless. The solvent was removed from the total dark coloured extract (2 litres) at a bath temperature of 40°. The resulting extractive was further dried under vacuum when a brown resinous material was obtained, which could be easily powdered. It was carefully dried in a vacuum desiccator over calcium chloride. The substance (48 g.) was dissolved in anhydrous benzene (600 c.c.) and the solution was passed through a battery of five columns of neutral alumina (BDH), each column containing 150 g. of alumina. The substance was eluted with benzene and the light greenish yellow solutions, collected mostly from the middle fractions of the eluates, were combined together (750 c.c.) and the solvent removed completely under vacuum. The residue (about 8 g.), on extraction with petroleum ether (b.p. 40°-60°), yielded a yellow oil (4.8 g., 1%) which darkened on keeping and a very small quantity of a substance, crystallising from ethyl acetate in colorless microneedles, m.p. 74-75° (total yield 10 mg.). It showed no colour reaction with alcoholic ferric chloride solution. (Found: C, 80.1; H, 12.80. C₁₄H₁₂O requires C, 80.29; H, 12.58 per cent). The petroleum ether-insoluble fraction was dissolved in excess of alcohol and left in the cold room for 24 hours, when a yellow product was

obtained in a very poor yield, crystallising from ethyl acetate in light yellow needles, m.p. 216-17° (total yield about 5 mg.); it showed no colour reaction with ferric chloride-alcohol. (Found: C, 68.14; H, 5.06. $C_{20}H_{18}O_6$ requires C, 67.79; H, 5.12 per cent).

These two substances could not be obtained in sufficient quantity for their characterisation. The mother-liquor after removing the substance of m.p. 216-17°, on concentration yielded the main crystalline constituent which was finally crystallised from a mixture of chloroform-alcohol and was obtained as rectangular prisms, m.p. 192-93° (total yield 1.45 g.). In subsequent experiments the substance of m.p. 216-17° was either not obtained at all or isolated in negligible amount.

The best result for the isolation of munetone was obtained when the dry powdered ethereal extract of the root-bark was first treated with petroleum ether (b.p. 40°-60°) for a number of times and the petroleum ether-insoluble material was dried and chromatographed in the usual way. Following this method, it was observed that the particular light greenish yellow eluate, on removal of the solvent, deposited the crystalline munetone.

Munetone was further chromatographed through alumina in benzene-petroleum ether but the melting point could not be raised. It is readily soluble in benzene, chloroform and ethyl acetate; fairly so in ether and acetone; sparingly soluble in methyl and ethyl alcohol and insoluble in petroleum ether. (Found: C, 74.98, 74.82; H, 5.78, 5.95; OMe, 9.04, 8.4. $C_{21}H_{18}O_4$ requires C, 75.43; H, 5.43; OMe, 9.28 per cent).

Oximation of Munetone.—Munetone (120 mg.) was dissolved in 98% alcohol (5 c.c.) and refluxed on a water-bath for 18 hours with hydroxylamine hydrochloride (0.5 g.) and fused sodium acetate (1 g.). The reaction mixture was cooled and poured into excess of cold water. The precipitated oxime was filtered, dried and crystallised from 90% alcohol in colorless rectangular plates (100 mg.), m.p. 205°-210° (decomp.). Repeated attempts to get a constant melting substance were unsuccessful. This may be due to the oxime being formed as a mixture of *cis-trans* isomers. It showed no coloration with ferric chloride-alcohol. (Found: C, 71.9; H, 5.62; N, 3.8. $C_{21}H_{18}O_4N$ requires C, 72.19; H, 5.48; N, 4.01 per cent).

Bromo Derivative of Munetone.—Munetone (100 mg.) was taken in CCl_4 (2 c.c.) and a solution of bromine in CCl_4 was slowly added till a distinct colour of bromine persisted. On removal of the solvent and crystallising the residue from 90% alcohol, the bromo compound was obtained as colorless prisms, m.p. 207° (decomp.), yield 90 mg. (Found: Br, 31.7. $C_{21}H_{18}O_4Br_2$ requires Br, 32.3 per cent).

Hydrolysis of Munetone to Munetol and Formic Acid.—Munetone (1 g.) was refluxed for 2 hours on a water-bath with 3% alcoholic potash (20 c.c.). The solution was cooled and acidified with dilute phosphoric acid, when the ketone (munetol) was precipitated. It was filtered, washed with water and dried; yield of crude ketone, 0.93 g. On crystallising from 90% alcohol, it was obtained as light yellow needles, m.p. 128°. It developed a deep green colour with ferric chloride-alcohol. (Found: C, 74.11, 73.76, 73.97; H, 6.5, 6.67, 6.44. $C_{20}H_{20}O_4$ requires C, 74.05; H, 6.22 per cent).

The aqueous layer in the above operation was steam-distilled. The distillate gave positive test for formic acid when subjected to formaldehyde-chromotropic

acid test, which was carried out as follows: A few drops of the sample solution was mixed in a test tube with a drop of 2*N*-HCl; magnesium powder was then added until no further gas was liberated. H₂SO₄ (3 c.c.) and a little chromotropic acid were then added; the tube was heated for 10 minutes at about 60°, when a violet-pink colour appeared. Parallel experiments with distilled water and very dilute formic acid were made for comparison.

Munetol was also obtained on reductive hydrolysis of munetone with zinc dust and alkali in alcoholic solution.

Oximation of Munetol.—A mixture of munetol (100 mg.), hydroxylamine hydrochloride (200 mg.), fused sodium acetate (500 mg.) and 98% alcohol (7 c.c.) was refluxed on a water-bath for 8 hours. On working up the product, the oxime was crystallised from methyl alcohol as colorless prisms, m.p. 224° (decomp.), yield 80 mg. It gives a deep green colour with ferric chloride-alcohol. The oxime on keeping darkens in colour as a yellow product. (Found: C, 71.04, 71.06; H, 6.17, 6.16; N, 3.77, 3.5. C₂₀H₂₁O₄N requires C, 70.78; H, 6.24; N, 4.13 per cent).

Methyl Ester of Munetol.—A mixture of munetol (200 mg.), anhydrous potassium carbonate (1 g.), acetone (10 c.c.) and dimethyl sulphate (4 c.c.) was refluxed for 16 hours. The solution was cooled and poured into excess of water. The precipitated compound was filtered, dried and crystallised from 90% alcohol, when the methyl ester of munetol was obtained as colorless prisms, m.p. 139°, yield 150 mg. It showed no coloration with ferric chloride-alcohol. (Found: C, 74.27, 74.40; H, 6.86, 6.60. C₂₁H₂₂O₄ requires C, 74.53; H, 6.55 per cent).

Acetylation of Munetol.—A mixture of munetol (100 mg.), fused sodium acetate (1 g.) and acetic anhydride (3 c.c.) was refluxed at about 150° for 3 hours. Water was added to the cooled reaction mixture when the solid slowly precipitated, which was filtered and crystallised from methyl alcohol. The methylisoflavone derivative was obtained as colorless clusters of needles, m.p. 227° (yield 40 mg.) and it showed no coloration with ferric chloride-alcohol. (Found: C, 75.35; H, 6.03. C₂₂H₂₂O₄ requires C, 75.84; H, 5.79 per cent).

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